

A STRATEGIC TECHNOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE LIQUEFIED PETROLEUM GAS RETAIL INDUSTRY IN ILE-IFE, OSUN STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study determined total cooking energy and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) consumption in Ile-Ife, assessed selected technographic parameters of the LPG retail sector, and analysed safety and environmental considerations of the industry as critical intelligence towards the strategic characterization of the industry. An energy planning/technology foresight analysis framework was used entailing geospatial imagery, questionnaire administration and site visitation to LPG retail outlets in the study area. Data collected were analysed using industrial and energy/environment process calculations, descriptive statistics, and a standard safety assessment indicator tool. Results showed an estimated total cooking energy demand/month of 46.152 million BTU by 79.5 thousand households. Identified LPG retail facilities were Industrial Storage “Category A” (6), Gas retail station Add-ons (13), and Resellers/“Category D” local dealers (78), with 68% of them located in close proximity to the University and its Teaching Hospital. Total estimated monthly LPG sales and revenues were 131,600 kg and ₦ 154.74 million respectively. The cooking energy consumption consisted of LPG (13.3%) and probable biomass content (86.7%), generating 394.8 Tonnes and between 4,670 – 5,810 Tonnes of carbon-dioxide respectively. Industry safety assessment ratings revealed that industrial storage facilities were rated very good, add-on in Retail station categories were satisfactory while reseller type outlets were rated poor. The study concluded that LPG consumption was low albeit more environmentally viable; the Industrial Storage/Retail station add-on types dominated the local LPG retail industry with satisfactory safety status; while the Reseller type outlets were most widespread, had poor safety status, and consequently high hazard susceptibility. LPG consumption and safety enhancement measures were recommended.

Keywords: Liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), Cooking energy, Safety assessment, Clean energy, Carbon-dioxide emissions reduction, Energy planning analysis, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Energy is fundamental to human life and the ability of any nation to carry out work and attain sustainable development (Ahmed, 2023). In fact, energy consumption parameters are a standard measure of the development of nations and has significant correlations with Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Human Development Index (HDI) (Imran and Ozcatalbas, 2016; Ogundari, 2023). Nations desire energy being available, accessible, adequate, affordable and clean. Energy is used in transportation, industry, agriculture and residential sectors of national economies. In the residential sector, cooking energy is a significant percentage of sectoral demand.

In Nigeria, like other developing countries, cooking energy is almost 90% of total residential energy demand. Furthermore, cooking energy is predominantly (about 65 – 85.5%) dependent on biomass energy sources (such as wood, charcoal, agricultural waste and animal dung), unlike developed societies which rely on modern, clean cooking fuels (such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), electricity, and biogas/biofuel gels) (Emagbetere *et al.*, 2016; Garba and Bellingham, 2021; Kojima, 2021). High income urban

dwellers prefer LPG and electricity for cooking while low/medium income urban and rural community dwellers prefer biomass (Emagbetere *et al.*, 2016). Factors influencing household cooking energy choices include household income, trend, ease of use, accessibility, cost of energy, and cleanliness (Arowolo *et al.*, 2018).

The drive in developing societies like Nigeria is to achieve the status of developed societies which rely on the clean cooking phenomenon premised on the identified modern, clean cooking fuels. Clean cooking entails the use of energy-efficient, time-saving, environmentally-friendly and health-conscious technologies and techniques for cooking food (Imran and Ozcatalbas, 2016; NIEP, 2022). This is in place of the traditional cooking techniques premised on biomass sources which are anything but ‘energy-efficient, time saving, environmentally-friendly and health-conscious’. Clean cooking promotes health improvement, environmental protection, household finances and gender equality (Liu *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Although, in Nigeria, government is aware of these benefits, constraints to clean cooking adoption include financial and economic barriers, technical and infrastructure limitations, socio-cultural behaviour, awareness and education, logistics and

supply chain limitations, and public policy and regulatory challenges.

Amongst the four modern cooking fuels identified – liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), electricity, solar energy and biogas/biofuel gels – the liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) option has been dominant in Nigeria over many years. LPG is a flammable mixture of hydrocarbon gases (mainly propane and butane) produced during crude oil refining or extracted from natural gas streams (Huth *et al.*, 2013). It is stored in liquid form under moderate pressure for easy transportation and usage. It has high energy content making it an efficient fuel, consequently it is widely used as a residential, commercial, industrial or automotive fuel specifically for heating, cooking and alternative to petrol and diesel in internal combustion engines (autogas). LPG is a major energy source due to its efficiency, versatility, and clean-burning nature with less environmental impact relative to other fossil fuels (Kumar and Singh, 2022).

The LPG retail industry in Nigeria is a significant section of the national energy market, and entails the distribution and sale of LPG to consumers throughout the Country primarily for cooking and heating. The autogas business component in Nigeria is not well developed (Nwafor and Akinola, 2022). The industry is highly competitive, with many players; it has a market structure comprising large suppliers and distributors (who deal with bulk supplies and own huge tank-farms) and local dealers/retailers (who focus on small businesses, households and end-users, selling in cylinders of different sizes like 6, 12.5 and 50kg) (Oluwole and Igbalajobi 2021). The LPG industry is open and highly competitive, the market is deregulated, and pricing is market-based, albeit industry regulation is weak. Although growth opportunities for the industry abound in Nigeria, especially with the various national/sub-national clean energy initiatives and tech-business development campaigns, there are challenges of crude oil pricing and foreign exchange rate fluctuations that lead to astronomical increases in domestic prices and stifle domestic consumer demand (Nwafor and Akinola, 2022).

Specifically, policy measures by the Nigerian Government to improve LPG utilization as cooking fuel include the National Gas Expansion Programme (NGEP), the Decade of Gas Outreach Programme (with the aim to move one million homes to clean cooking gas by 2030), infrastructure development (such as storage facilities regionally) to strengthen the LPG supply chain and distribution, publicity and awareness on LPG benefits, and regulatory reforms for LPG industry growth (Adekoya and Okeniyi, 2019; Akinola and Bolaji, 2020; NIEP, 2022). Government efforts in Nigeria over the years to grow the domestic LPG sector have taken into cognizance the huge national proven natural gas reserves (estimated at 206.53 trillion cubic feet as at 2021) located both offshore and onshore with the Niger Delta region being the epicenter (Lawal and Adeoye, 2022; NMDPRA, 2023). The growth of national LPG consumption over the last 25 years, with demand increasing from less than 50,000 metric Tonnes in 2000 to over a 1

million metric Tonnes by 2022, has been facilitated by government policies, the increasing population coupled with rapid urbanization, the rising middle class and increased household incomes, and the developing environmental and health awareness of LPG as a cleaner cooking energy relative to traditional cooking fuels like firewood and charcoal demand (Adekoya and Okeniyi, 2019; Ekewchukwu and Obianyo, 2021; Olatunji *et al.*, 2021; Adepoju and Afolabi, 2022; Nwafor and Akinola, 2022).

In spite of recent improvements in the LPG sector in Nigeria (NMDPRA, 2023), challenges facing the retail industry include infrastructure deficits, regulatory and safety concerns, supply chain and price volatility, product affordability and accessibility (Adekoya and Okeniyi, 2019; Igbokwe and Enyi, 2020; Abiodun and Ayodele, 2021; Adepoju and Afolabi, 2022). The largely informal nature of the LPG market has further accentuated limited information on the industry's characteristics and business operations (Nnaji and Ubani, 2020; Oteh and Isife, 2020; Babatunde and Akanbi, 2020).

At the sub-national level, there is even greater limitation on the availability of information on the LPG industry's characteristics and operations in individual States (Nnaji and Ubani, 2020; Abiodun and Ayodele, 2021; Adepoju and Afolabi, 2022). This viewpoint is particularly true for Osun State, thus making it imperative to provide a strategic assessment of the LPG retail industry's characteristics and operations as critical policy intelligence for LPG-sector policy development in the State. The Ife Zone was purposively selected, as it has one of the most complex regional dynamics in the State due to its population (the highest in the State), urban nature due to the presence of Federal Government institutions like the University and Teaching Hospital, and its rural characteristic as the ancient cradle of the Yoruba race.

Consequent to the intentions of assessing the LPG retail industry in Osun State for strategic policy development, this study's objectives were to determine total cooking energy and LPG consumption in Ile-Ife, assess the technographic parameters of the LG facilities in the study area, and analyse safety and environmental considerations of the industry.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilised an energy planning and technology foresight analysis. Technology Foresight Analysis is a systematic, participatory process using collective intelligence for informed decision-making in exploring and shaping a strategic future for an organisation or society (Yim, 2010). It is most suitable for planning a desired energy future in a region. The TFA methods are Quantitative (benchmarking, modelling-simulation, extrapolation etc.), Semi-quantitative (road mapping, gaming-simulation, Delphi Technique, strategic assessment, etc.), and Qualitative (backcasting, genius-forecasting, expert panels, SWOT scanning, etc.) (Yim,

2010). These methods can be used independently or in combination.

Definition of technographic Parameters

Technographic parameters are specific data points that describe an individual's, organization's or market's use technology, or the technological characteristics of individuals, organizations or markets. In an operational context, technographic parameters help understand the technological behaviours, preferences and infrastructures (technological landscape or technology profile) of target audiences, and are useful in optimizing business strategies (operations, marketing, product development, etc). Technographic parameters include structure and roles, software and tools, hardware and infrastructure, investments and budgets, location profiling, technology adoption, innovation trends, consumption patterns, and market segmentation amongst others (Miller and Jackson, 2019; Gopal and Gupta, 2020; Roseunbaum and Cruz, 2021; Breeden and Garrett, 2022; Kats and Singh, 2022; Smith and Lim, 2022).

For this study, the technographic parameters analysed were the classification, number and location of LPG retail outlets, their techno-economic characteristics, the LPG to total cooking energy consumption, the estimated cooking energy demand, replacement cooking energy sources and demand, and carbon dioxide emissions.

The study area

As earlier stated, the Ife Zone was purposively selected, as it has one of the most complex regional dynamics in the State. Ile-Ife is an ancient Yoruba city in Osun State, South-West Nigeria, and with an estimated population of 462,000 people, has the highest population in the State. It is recognized as the ancestral home of the Yoruba people worldwide, and mythologically considered the birthplace of humankind. Ile-Ife is about 218 kilometers Northeast of Lagos on longitude 4° 69'E and latitude 70° 50' N, covers a total area of 1,791 km², and consists of 2 Local Government Areas (LGAs) – Ife Central and Ife East LGAs. Ile-Ife was founded between 1000 – 600 BC, and is largely inhabited by the Yoruba people. Ile-Ife is home to many public and private academic and research institutions like the prestigious Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), Ile-Ife, the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospital Complex (OAUTHC), National Centre for Technology Management (NACETEM), the Centre for Energy Research and Development (CERD), the African Regional Centre for Space Science & Technology Education - English (ARCSSTEE), and the African Regional Institute for Geospatial Information Science & Technology (AFRIGIST) amongst others. Major occupations in the Town are trading, farming and artisanal activities. The many academic and research centers have expanded educational sector occupations, with banks and the civil service also providing employment.

Methods of data collection

The estimated population of Ile-Ife as at 2022, the population growth rate, and the estimate number of occupants/ household were obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics. The estimated average cooking energy demand/household/per month in Southwestern Nigeria as well as their corresponding LPG equivalence in Kg were obtained from relevant research articles and assumed for Ile-Ife. From these data, the estimated population of Ile-Ife as at 2024, the number of households, the total cooking energy demand/month (measured in British Thermal Units (BTU)), and the LPG equivalence of this total cooking energy demand/month (measured in Kg) were calculated.

The classification of LPG retail outlets (the categories and their corresponding size of storage vessels) were obtained from the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) (2018) publication. A list of registered LPG retailers in Ile-Ife was obtained from the Liquefied Petroleum Gas Retail Association (LPGRA) in Osun State (Ile-Ife Branch). Thereafter, utilizing Google Map (a form of remote sensing) and site visitations, the location of the LPG retail outlets were determined. These retail outlets were consequently appropriately categorized and their numbers determined. The identified LPG Resellers ("Category D") were administered the questionnaire through their association and the number and percentage of returnees determined. A combined survey and interview technique was used to obtain selected technographic data from the identified LPG retail outlets (the LPG Industrial Storage "Category A", LPG Add-on in Retail Stations, and LPG resellers).

Two sets of safety assessment questionnaire were administered on the identified LPG retail outlets to obtain safety competence data. Energy, carbon-dioxide emissions and techno-economic conversion factors were obtained from the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN) repository, related energy research articles, and industrial process calculation textbooks. Population and household data were obtained from the websites of the Osun State Government and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS).

The data was analysed using industrial/energy process calculations, descriptive statistics, Google maps for geospatial imagery, and carbon emissions calculations where appropriate.

Analytical tools

Determining the total cooking energy demand and LPG consumption in Ile-Ife entailed using industrial and energy process calculations as well as descriptive statistics. The analysis of the technographic characteristics of the LPG facilities entailed using descriptive statistics and Google maps for geospatial imagery. Assessment of the environmental parameters of the LPG retail industry entailed using energy/environment process calculations, while the safety assessment utilized a quantitative Health & Safety Management Standards Indicator Tool.

A. The determination of total cooking energy and LPG consumption in Ile-Ife

- i. The estimation of the Ile-Ife population in 2024 entailed a Compound Interest Formula (Ogunleye and Adebayo, 2019; Adegoke and Akindele, 2020; Adesina and Ajayi, 2021, Akinyemi and Adewuyi, 2022; Citypopulation.de, 2022)

$$\text{New Population} = \text{Principal Population as at Y2022} (1 + \text{Rate})^{\text{Time}} \quad (1)$$

Where,

Principal Population = 462,000 (Citypopulation.de (2022))

Rate of population growth = 1.6% Citypopulation.de (2022)

Time from 2022 to 2024 = 2 years

- ii. Number of Occupants/household in Southwestern Nigeria = 6 (REF)

$$\text{iii. Number of Households in Ile-Ife} = \frac{\text{New Population}}{\text{Number of Occupants/Household}} \quad (2)$$

- iv. Estimated cooking energy demand/household/month = 580,650 BTU (Ogundari, 2023)

$$\text{v. Total Cooking Energy Demand/Month (BTU)} = \text{Estimated cooking energy demand/household/month} \times \text{Number of Households} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{vii. The LPG Equivalence is determined by} \frac{\text{Total Cooking Energy Demand/Month (BTU)}}{46,452 \text{ BTU}} \quad (3)$$

B. The determination of techno-economic characteristics of LPG facilities in Ile-Ife

- ii. Average monthly sales/plant = $\frac{\text{Total Monthly Sales of all Plants/month}}{\text{Total Number of Plants}}$ (4)

$$\text{iii. Total Monthly Sales} = \text{Number of LPG Plants} \times \text{Average monthly sales/plant} \quad (5)$$

- iv. LPG Price (₦/Kg) were obtained from DPR
- v. Total Monthly Revenue (₦ '10⁶) = LPG Price (₦/Kg) X Total Monthly Sales (6)

- vi. Average Number of Employees/Plant were obtained from the study
- vii. Total Number of Employees = Number of LPG plants X Average Number of Employees per plant (7)

C. The estimation of cooking energy demand, comparative cooking energy sources and carbon dioxide emissions in Ile-Ife

- i. Estimated total cooking energy demand was obtained from the study
- ii. LPG Consumption in BTU = determined from conversion of LPG Consumption in Kg to BTU
- iii. CO₂ emissions from LPG consumption (Kg) = LPG Consumption (Kg) X 3. (8)
- iv. Difference in energy consumption = Estimated total cooking energy demand – LPG Consumption (9)
- v. Estimating probable biomass sources for the difference in energy consumption:

- a. Wood (air seasoned) as source for estimated total cooking energy demand (Kg) = $\frac{\text{Total cooking energy demand}}{15,449.42 \text{ BTU}}$ (10)

- b. CO₂ emissions from Wood (Air seasoned) consumption (Kg) = Wood Consumption (Kg) X 1.8. (11)

- c. Charcoal as source for estimated total cooking energy demand (Kg) = $\frac{\text{Total cooking energy demand}}{22,747.61 \text{ BTU}}$ (12)

- d. CO₂ emissions from Charcoal consumption (Kg) = Charcoal Consumption (Kg) X 1.8. (13)

NOTE:

1 kg LPG ≡ 3 kg CO₂ ≡ 49.01 MJ ≡ 46,452 BTU
 1 kg Wood (Air Seasoned) ≡ 1.65 to 1.8 kg CO₂ ≡ 16.3 MJ ≡ 15,449.42 BTU
 1 kg Charcoal ≡ 3.3 kg CO₂ ≡ 24 MJ ≡ 22,747.61 BTU

D. The estimation of cooking energy demand, replacement cooking energy sources and carbon dioxide emissions in Ile-Ife

- i. Estimated total cooking energy demand was obtained from the study
- ii. Estimating replacement cooking energy sources for the cooking energy demand:

- a. LPG equivalence in Kg determined by $\frac{\text{Total cooking energy demand}}{46,452 \text{ BTU}}$ (14)

- b. CO₂ emissions from LPG equivalence consumption (Kg) = LPG Consumption (Kg) X 3.

- c. Wood (air seasoned) equivalence in Kg determined by $\frac{\text{Total cooking energy demand}}{15,449.42 \text{ BTU}}$ (16)

- d. CO₂ emissions from Wood (Air seasoned) consumption (Kg) = Wood Consumption (Kg) X 1.8. (17)

e. Charcoal equivalence in Kg determined by =
$$\frac{\text{Total cooking energy demand}}{22,747.61 \text{ BTU}} \quad (18)$$

f. CO₂ emissions from Charcoal consumption (Kg) = Charcoal Consumption (Kg) X 1.8.
$$(19)$$

NOTE:

- 1 kg LPG ≡ 3 kg CO₂ ≡ 49.01 MJ ≡ 46,452 BTU
- 1 kg Wood (Air Seasoned) ≡ 1.65 to 1.8 kg CO₂ ≡ 16.3 MJ ≡ 15,449.42 BTU
- 1 kg Charcoal ≡ 3.3 kg CO₂ ≡ 24 MJ ≡ 22,747.61 BTU

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Technographic parameters of LPG facilities in Ile-Ife

There are 6 categories of licenses for LPG stations according to Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR)

guidelines, five of which are designed to feed the household cooking sector. These are listed in Table 3.2. The Table shows that there are no LPG refilling plants in the study area, there are 6 LPG Industrial Storage “Category A” facilities, 13 LPG Add-on in Gas retail stations, and 78 LPG resellers or “Category D” local dealers.

Plate 3.1 shows the graphical location of LPG facilities in Ile-Ife. These facilities are indicated in the red gas stations. They are majorly situated along the urbanized sections of the city, and predominantly in close proximity to the University and the University Teaching Hospital (13 out of 19 facilities – 68.4%). The University is indicated by the blue building, the blue circle indicates the University and University Teaching Hospital area. This is not surprising as this area has the highest number of educated, urbanized people in the City represented by university students, University Faculty and Administrators, Medical

Table 3.1: Estimated Cooking Energy Consumption in Ile-Ife

Population	Number of Occupants/Household	Number of Households	Estimated Cooking Energy Demand/Household/Month (BTU)	Total Cooking Energy Demand/Month (BTU)	LPG Equivalence (Kg)
476,903	6	79,484	580,650	46,152,384,600	993,550

Table 3.2: Types of LPG Facilities in Ile-Ife

Categories	Size of Storage Vessels	Number
LPG Refilling Plant (above ground storage tanks)	5 – 300 metric Tonnes	0
LPG Refilling Plant (underground storage tanks)	5 – 300 metric Tonnes	0
LPG Industrial Storage “Category A”	> 500kg in fixed vessel	6
LPG Add-on in Retail Stations	1 – 5 Metric Tonnes	13
LPG Resellers (“Category D”)	A combination of 50kg, 25kg, 12.5kg, 6kg and 3kg cylinders totaling up to 500kg Storage Capacity	78

Plate 3.1: Location of LPG Service Stations in Ile-Ife

Professionals, financial services personnel and other professionals. They are also indicative of the type of people who would use modern energy sources (Ogundari *et al.*, 2024).

It is important to note that the 6 LPG Industrial Storage “Storage A” facilities and 13 LPG Add-ons in Gas retail stations are located appropriately in designated areas in adherence to approved government regulations, the LPG resellers or “Category D” local dealers are located haphazardly around the town, especially along major roads, and situated in the midst of residential and commercial buildings. The erratic distribution and specific location of LPG retail outlets constitute a crucial safety breach and pose grave and imminent danger to the neighbourhoods in which they are situated.

Table 3.3 reveals techno-economic parameters of the LPG facilities. The 6 LPG Industrial storage “Category A” and the LPG Add-on retail stations are the primary supply sources of LPG in Ile-Ife. Their supply sources are outside the City; they also operate independent of one another. The LPG Resellers/ “Category D” operators in Ile-Ife obtain their LPG supplies from either one of the primary suppliers. The 6 “Category A” stations have average total monthly

131,600 kg with average estimated revenue of ₦ 155.76 million.

This study argues that the 78 LPG resellers/“Category D” dealers in the city source their supply exclusively from the 6 Category A and 13 LPG Add-on retail stations, thus their sales are incorporated in the determined LPG consumption and revenue estimates. The 78 LPG resellers, with average total sales of 42,900 kg/month, account for only 32.6% of LPG sales in Ile-Ife.

This study has estimated total cooking energy demand/household/month in Ile-Ife to be 46.15 Million BTU (equivalent to 993,550 kg of LPG). The study has further estimated LPG consumption per month in Ile-Ife to be 131,600 kg. This suggests that actual LPG consumption is only 13.3% of estimated total cooking energy demand in Ile-Ife (see Chart 3.1). This further suggests that 86.7% of estimated total cooking energy demand in Ile-Ife is sourced from non-LPG supply which most likely would-be biomass sources (wood fuels, charcoal, agriculture residues, sawdust, etc) due to the rustic nature of the majority of the Ile-Ife population. This huge probable biomass consumption would have significant health, safety and environmental implications for the city.

Table 3.3: Techno-economic Characteristics of LPG Facilities in Ile-Ife

Categories	Number	Average Monthly Sales (Kg)	Total Monthly Sales (Kg)	Average Price (₦/Kg)	Total Monthly Revenue (₦ '106)	Average Number of Employees/Plant	Total Number of Employees
1. LPG Industrial Storage (“Category A”)	6	7200	43,200	1150	49.68	3	18
2. LPG Add-on in Retail Stations	13	6800	88,400	1200	106.08	2	26
3. LPG Resellers (“Category D”)	78	550	42,900	1400	60.06	1	78

Chart 3.1: LPG to Total Cooking Energy Consumption in Ile-Ife

sales of 43,200 kg combined, making an average estimated total revenue of ₦ 49.68 million per month. The 13 LPG Add-on retail stations have average total monthly sales of 88,400 kg combined, making an average estimated total revenue of ₦ 106.08 million per month. Thus, the average estimated total LPG consumption per month in Ile-Ife is

Safety and Environmental Considerations to the LPG and Probable Cooking Energy Sources in Ile-Ife

The estimated LPG consumption in Ile-Ife (131,600 Kg) would generate 6.11 million BTU of heat and would have

projected carbon dioxide emissions of 394.8 Tonnes (see Table 3.4). The estimated difference in cooking energy demand (40.039 Million BTU) could be sourced from probable biomass sources like air seasoned wood or charcoal. Table 3.4 shows that if the biomass source were air seasoned wood, 2.59 Thousand Tonnes would be required, producing 4.66 Thousand Tonnes of carbon dioxide emissions. If the biomass source was charcoal, 1.76 Thousand Tonnes would be required, producing 5.81 Thousand Tonnes of carbon-dioxide emissions. Or it would be a mix of both biomass sources, with their corresponding blend of feedstock requirements and carbon-dioxide emissions. Table 3.4 further shows that although the LPG consumption would produce a huge amount of carbon-dioxide (394.8 Tonnes) it is very small compared to the amount of carbon-dioxide produced from the probable biomass sources. Table 3.5 shows the projections if the estimated total cooking energy demand in Ile-Ife (46.15 Million BTU) were completely replaced with either one of LPG, air seasoned wood or charcoal in its totality. As the table reveals complete replacement by LPG would produce less carbon-dioxide emissions (2.98 Thousand Tonnes) than either air conditioned wood (carbon-dioxide emissions of 5.38 Thousand Tonnes) or charcoal (carbon-dioxide emissions of 6.7 Thousand Tonnes). Although LPG itself produced a significant amount of carbon-dioxide, air conditioned wood and charcoal produced 1.8 and 2.25 times more carbon-dioxide respectively. This is further evidence that LPG is a cleaner fuel relative to wood or charcoal.

Safety assessment of LPG retail stations operation and facility

The assessment of safety in the LPG retail industry in Ile-Ife entailed determining two key indicators, namely, the status of safety measures and the level of safety. In Table 3.6, the individual safety measure categories indicate the percentage of the outlets in each LPG retail type that are in adherence to the measures. This is an indicator of the safety competences of the LPG retail industry in Ile-Ife.

The Table reveals holistically, that for each safety measure, the Industrial Storage and Add-on in Retail station categories of LPG types had higher percentages of their outlets adhering to safety measures relative to the Reseller type outlets. This indicates that these two categories of the LPG retail industry are more safety compliant relative to the Reseller type outlets. This is a welcome assessment as the Industrial Storage and Add-on in Retail station categories are the major sources of LPG holdings in Ile-Ife. Bearing in mind the erratic distribution and specific locations of LPG retail outlets in Ile-Ife, the indication of low percentage of the outlets adhering to safety measures raises concerns. The Table showcases that the LPG industry in Ile-Ife was fraught with safety limitations with the Reseller outlet types being the major contributor to these limitations. For instance, all the Industrial storage outlets (100%) and most of the add-on retail stations (70-100%) adhered to the LPG storage and handling safety measures; whereas amongst the Resellers (Category D) type outlets, less than 50% did so. In fact, only a low 38% of the

Table 3.4: Estimated Cooking Energy Demand, Comparative Cooking Energy Sources and Carbon Dioxide Emissions in Ile-Ife

	Kg	BTU	CO ₂ Emission (Kg)
Estimated Total Cooking Energy Demand		46,152,384,600	
<u>LPG Consumption</u>	131,600	<u>6,113,083,200</u>	394,800
Difference		40,039,301,400	
Assuming Probable Biomass Source:			
Wood (Air Seasoned)	2,591,637.84	40,039,301,400	4,664,948.10
Charcoal	1,760,154.21	40,039,301,400	5,808,508.88

Table 3.5: Estimated Total Cooking Energy Demand, Replacement Cooking Energy Sources and Carbon Dioxide Emissions in Ile-Ife

	Kg	CO ₂ Emission(Kg)
Estimated Total Cooking Energy Demand		
46,152,384,600 BTU		
Replacement Cooking Energy Sources:		
LPG Equivalence	993,550	2,980,650
Wood Equivalence	2,987,321.51	5,377,178,71
Charcoal Equivalence	2,028,889.39	6,695,334.99

NOTE:

- 1 kg LPG \equiv 3 kg CO₂ \equiv 49.01 MJ \equiv 46,452 BTU
- 1 kg Wood (Air Seasoned) \equiv 1.65 to 1.8 kg CO₂ \equiv 16.3 MJ \equiv 15,449.42 BTU
- 1 kg Charcoal \equiv 3.3 kg CO₂ \equiv 24 MJ \equiv 22,747.61 BTU

Reseller stored their LPG cylinders in well ventilated areas away from ignition outlets.

For the Industrial storage category, a low percentage of their outlets adhered to safety measures in the following categories – fire prevention systems installation (33.3%), ventilation systems installation (33.3%), LPG cylinder labelling with safety guidelines (33.3%), conducting

emergency drills (33.3%), developing and implementing emergency response plans (33.3%), installing gas leak detectors (33.3%), and providing Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) (33.3%). It may not be surprising that it is the same 2 outlets that have these safety limitations.

For the add-on retail station category, low percentage of their outlets adhered to safety measures in the following categories – fire prevention systems installation (20%),

The Reseller type outlets were the most ill-prepared safety-wise. A high percentage of them did not adhere to fire safety measures (86-100%), did not install ventilation systems (100%), did not display content or safety instruction on LPG cylinders (74%), were deficient in training and awareness activities (86%) as well as emergency procedures (54-74%), lacked equipment maintenance (58-62%), had limited gas leak detection capabilities (78-100%), did not provide Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) (88%) or

Table 3.6: Status of Safety Measures amongst LPG Retail Outlets in Ile-Ife

	Industrial Storage (“Category A”) – 6		Add-on in Retail Stations – 10		Resellers (“Category D”) – 50	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. Storage and Handling						
Store LPG cylinders in well-ventilated space away from ignition sources	6	100	10	100	19	38
Secure cylinders to prevent tipping						
Use appropriate equipment for cylinder handling and transportation	6	100	8	80	21	42
	6	100	7	70	21	42
Fire Safety						
Install fire extinguishers	6	100	7	70	7	14
Ensure regular maintenance of fire extinguisher	5	83.3	4	40	7	14
Install fire detection and alarm systems	2	33.3	2	20	0	0
Train staff in fire safety procedures and emergency responses	4	66.7	3	30	7	14
Ventilation						
Ensure proper ventilation to prevent gas accumulation	6	100	10	100	27	54
Install ventilation systems in storage and dispensing areas	2	33.3	1	10	0	0
Signage and Labels						
Display warning signs (LPG presence and no-smoking signs)	6	100	10	100	50	100
Label cylinders clearly with contents and safety instructions	2	33.3	3	30	13	26
Training and Awareness						
Provide regular training for employees	3	50	2	20	7	14
Conduct emergency drills	2	33.3	1	10	7	14
Emergency Procedures						
Develop and implement emergency response plans	2	33.3	4	40	7	14
Ensure easy access to emergency contact numbers and procedures	6	100	7	70	23	46
Equipment Maintenance						
Regular inspection and maintenance of equipment	4	66.7	6	60	21	42
Replace damaged and worn-out equipment promptly	3	50	4	40	19	38
Leak Detection						
Install gas detectors for leak detection	2	33.3	2	20	0	0
Conduct regular leak tests for systems and connections	3	50	4	40	11	22
Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)						
Provide appropriate PPE for staff	2	33.3	2	20	9	18
Security						
Secure LPG storage area to prevent unauthorized access	6	100	6	60	7	14
Implement measures to prevent theft and vandalism	6	100	6	60	50	100
Compliance with Regulation						
Adhere to local, state, and national regulations	6	100	8	80	34	68
Stay updated on industry standards and best practices	5	83.3	6	60	17	34

training staff for fire procedures (30%), ventilation systems installation (10%), LPG cylinder labelling with safety guidelines (30%), providing regular employee training (20%), conducting emergency drills (10%), developing and implementing emergency response plans (40%), replacing damaged equipment promptly (40%), installing gas leak detectors (20%), conducting regular gas leak tests (40%), and providing Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) (20%).

adequately secure the LPG storage area to prevent unauthorized access (86%), nor stay updated with industry standards and best practices (66%).

More insight on safety competences by the LPG retail industry in Ile-Ife was provided by further analysis by Safety Professionals (see Table 3.5).

For the Industrial storage category, each safety indicator was at least considered Satisfactory, with the greatest

concerns being adoption of best practices for technological and engineering control (rated E – Poor) and Emergency Preparedness, where both measurements were rated only Adequate. The overall rating for safety in this category was Satisfactory at least and Very Good at best, indicating significant room for improvement.

For the add-on retail station category, the overall safety rating was Satisfactory, however too many indicators raised concerns including the reporting systems for incident and accident data (rated only D – Adequate), employee involvement in safety culture (rated E – Poor),

imperative that the safety level of this category be improved on as they dominate LPG supply in Ile-Ife.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study assessed the strategic technological parameters of the LPG retail industry in Ile-Ife as a critical input to strategic energy and industrial policy initiatives in Osun State. An energy planning/technology foresight analysis framework was used. The study provided information on

Table 3.7: Determination of Level of Safety in the Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) Retail Industry

	Industrial Storage (“Category A”) - 6	Add-on in Retail Stations - 10	Resellers (“Category D”) - 50
	Modal Rating	Modal Rating	Modal Rating
Regulatory Compliance			
Adherence to Standards	B	C	E
Certification and Licensing	B	C	E
Incident and Accident Data			
Historical Analysis (Review of past incidents, such as leaks, fires, or explosions, and near misses)	C	C	E
Reporting Systems (examination of the effectiveness and use of incident reporting systems. Are all safety incidents reported, documented, and acted upon?)	C	D	E
Safety Culture			
Training and Competence	B	C	E
Management Commitment	B	C	E
Employee Involvement	C	E	E
Risk Assessment			
Hazard Identification	B	B	C
Risk Control Measures/Mitigation Strategies	B	C	E
Safety Performance Indicators			
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) Monitoring	C	C	F
Benchmarking	D	E	F
Technological and Engineering Controls			
Safety Equipment	C	C	E
Adoption of Best Practices	E	E	F
Workplace Environment			
Storage Conditions	A	B	D
Handling and Transportation	B	C	E
Emergency Preparedness			
Emergency Response Plans (fire drills, leak response, etc)	D	E	F
Crisis Management	D	F	F
End-User Safety			
Customer Education	C	C	E
Product Safety	C	C	E
OVERALL RATING	B	C	E

Legend:

F: 0 – 39% Fail	E: 40 – 44% Poor	D: 45 – 49% Adequate	C: 50 – 59% Satisfactory	B: 60 – 69% Very Good	A: 70 – 100% Excellent
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benchmarking of Safety Performance Indicators (rated E – Poor), adoption of best practices for technological and engineering control (rated E – Poor), and Emergency Preparedness (emergency response planning was rated E – Poor; crisis management capacity was rated F – Fail). It is

total cooking energy and LPG consumption in Ile-Ife, technographic characteristics and safety and environmental considerations of the LPG retail sector in the town. The study determined total cooking energy demand/month in Ife at 46.152 million BTU. It identified three major LPG

retail facilities – Industrial Storage “Category A” (6), LPG Add-on in Gas retail stations (13), and Resellers or “Category D” local dealers (78) – with most of them (68%) situated close to the University and its Teaching Hospital, and having total estimated monthly LPG sales and revenues of 131,600 kg and ₦ 154.74 million respectively. The LPG consumed (13.3% of total cooking energy demand/month) generated 394.8 Tonnes of carbon-dioxide, a small fraction of the 4.67 – 5.81 Thousand Tonnes of carbon-dioxide emissions by the alternative cooking energy source (probably biomass). Industry safety assessments showed Satisfactory/Very Good and Satisfactory for Industrial Storage “Category A” and Add-on in Retail stations respectively, with the Reseller type outlets rated Poor. Deductions made included that the Industrial Storage and Add-on in Retail station categories dominated the Ife LPG retail industry with acceptable safety ratings, while the Reseller type outlets had the greatest safety risks. Their wide distribution and integration into neighbourhoods indicate that the hazards the Reseller type outlets were most susceptible to could have grave consequences like fire hazards and health issues in the neighbourhoods

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